

Advanced AI: Deep Reinforcement Learning in Data science

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INTRODUCTION:

Reinforcement Learning is the more futuristic sibling of supervised and unsupervised learning. So, if you follow Google Deepmind. Both the Atari and Go systems they built use deep reinforcement learning. Also, it is often used when you do not have a dataset in the first place but a heuristic as to what is good data.

AIM:

Build various deep learning agents and Apply a variety of advanced reinforcement learning algorithms for some Data science real life problem. Q-Learning with Deep Neural Networks for big data and predictive analysis. Policy Gradient Methods with Neural Networks.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Extend our knowledge of temporal difference learning by looking at the TD Lambda algorithm, we'll look at a special type of neural network called the RBF network, we'll look at the policy gradient method, and also looking at Deep Q-Learning.

RESULTS:

Unlike supervised and unsupervised learning algorithms, reinforcement learning agents have an impetus - they want to reach a goal. This is such a fascinating perspective, it can even make supervised / unsupervised machine learning and "data science" seem boring in hindsight. Why train a neural network to learn about the data in a database, when you can train a neural network to interact with the real-world. While deep reinforcement learning and AI has a lot of potential, it also carries with it huge risk.

CONCLUSIONS:

As compute speeds grow higher and costs lower we can visit increasingly larger subsets of the State space and examine more time delay options. Many of these solutions apply principles from neural nets, back propagation, evolutionary or annealing-like procedures, and factored structures all of which reside primarily in the realms of Supervised and Unsupervised learning. This cross over of domains can be confusing but where and how to apply RL is an increasingly important body of knowledge for data scientists.

KEYWORDS:

Deep reinforcement learning ; data science ; machine learning ; neural networks ; Advanced AI ; Q-Learning